

The Effect of Price and Location on Purchasing Decisions at Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine the effect of price and location on purchasing decisions at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin. Sources of data in this study are primary and secondary. Data collection techniques are by distributing questionnaires, observations, interviews, documentary studies, and literature studies. In this study, the population is consumers who come to the Green Pets Shop and make purchases or visits from January to December 2020 with an average number of 84 consumers obtained from weekly calculations. Analysis of the data used is multiple linear regression. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded as follows: 1) Price has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. Judging from the results of the calculation (X1) t-count is greater than (t-table) which is $5.074 > 2.028$ or (Sig $0.000 < 0.05$), this means that the price has a significant effect on purchasing decisions at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin, 2) Location has no significant effect. significant to purchasing decisions. Judging from the results of the calculation (X2) t-count is smaller than (t-table) i.e. $0.351 < 2.028$ or (Sig $0.728 > 0.05$), this means that location has no significant effect on purchasing decisions at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin. 3) Price and location have a significant effect on purchasing decisions at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin. Judging from the results of the calculation, F-count is greater than F-table, which is $19.594 > 3.26$. 4) The effect of price and location on purchasing decisions adjusted R square shows a value of 0.501, meaning that it has a contribution variance of 50.1% while the remaining 49.9% is explained by other variables not included in this study. Thus, it means that there is a significant effect between price and location on purchasing decisions at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin

Keywords:- price, location, purchase decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's globalization era has resulted in humans experiencing changes, both in the fields of economic politics, social, and culture and affecting competitiveness in managing a business so that everyone who has a business must think creatively and innovatively in managing the business they are in. The dynamic change in consumer mindset gives rise to business growth that continues to be competitive [1]. Along with the development of science and technology, people usually make instant, flexible and effective decisions.

One of them is the opportunity business from the demand for these pet needs to be called "Green Pets Shop". The greater the interest in raising animals, until it continues to be a big pattern of consumers who decide to buy products

from the business. Green Pets Shop sells products or services for complete animal health care with safe product quality according to the benefits of efficacy for pets, especially for cats.

The attitude of residents or modern society at this time has been dynamically demanding entrepreneurs to continue to understand the change of existing areas, as a consequence of life dynamics to make the business being run grow. The purchase process is a real process in purchasing, whether buying or not. This matter certainly depends on the willingness of consumers to carry out purchases. So that consumers are a very meaningful thing [2]. The process that is interpreted is from the will that arises in the consumer, after which the consumer decides whether the will they realize or not. Consumers who carry out the purchase process or not, have implemented the purchase decision.

Marketing philosophy underwent an evolution from an internal orientation (inward-looking) or inside-out perspective) to from an internal orientation (inward-looking) or inside-out perspective) to an external orientation (outward-looking or outside-looking perspective). Internal orientation is reflected in production orientation, product orientation and sales orientation, while external orientation is reflected in consumer orientation (also known as marketing concepts) and social marketing orientation (holistic marketing) [3].

Fig. 1: Marketing Perspectives

A product or service has some value and is generally valued in several money, which at this time we often call it price, and after that the consumer wants to exchange some definite value for some of the certain money, they have with the aim that they want to be able to own or use the product or service. So it can be said that the price of a product is a dimension to the size of a person's satisfaction with the product he bought.

Location is an area that makes the product available to the target customer. Location is the location of stores or retailers in strategic areas so that they can maximize profits [4]. Choosing the right business location will determine the

success of the business in the future. *Place* is a distribution decision that concerns ease of access to services for potential customers [5]. Location means in relation to where the company must be based and carry out its operations or activities.

The existence of different needs makes the company in this case adjust which one is effective and efficient in choosing a place or location to be set in doing business. There are several considerations in determining the choice of location, including [5]:

- Access, namely the ease of reaching, for example, the location through which is passed is easily accessible to public facilities / transportation.
- Visionability, that is, a location or place that can be clearly seen from normal visibility.
- Traffic concerns the following two main considerations:
 - The large number of people passing by can provide a great opportunity for impulse buying, namely purchasing decisions that occur spontaneously, without planning, and without going through special efforts.
 - Congestion and traffic congestion can be obstacles.

There are 2 factors that arise between the intention in making the decision to buy. The first factor is the attitude of

others and the second is the factor of unexpected situations After buying a product consumers will experience a process of satisfaction as a post-purchase behavior, which is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment of a person derived from a comparison between his impressions of the performance or results of a product and his expectations. If performance is below expectations, consumers are not satisfied. If the performance meets consumer expectations, it will cause satisfaction and pleasure.

From the results of a survey at the Green Pets Shop, it has certain tricks in ensuring the selling price of its merchandise, such as getting around the price game method, which is to lower some of the prices of some types of goods for attraction to consumers and to be re-prepared by increasing other types of objects. Then based on the results of the interview for the price of products sold at the Green Pets Shop is cheaper than the price of products in other Pets Shops, we can see from the production prices in the three Pets Shops, which researchers have calculated the average of the prices of products in the three Pets Shops. Here's an example of a comparison of prices and average results that are in demand at the Green Pets Shop that Pets Shop sells elsewhere.

Item Type	Green Pets Shop (IDR)	99 Pets Shop (IDR)	Naching Pets shop (IDR)
Bold Tuna 1kg	20.000	30.000	25.000
Excel 1kg	20.000	18.000	22.000
Felibet 1kg	22.000	20.000	25.000
Meo 1,2kg	50.000	50.000	60.000
Whiskas 480gr	26.000	28.000	30.000
Whiskas Sachet 85gr	6.000	6.000	6.000
Cat Choize Kitten	22.000	23.000	25.000
Plain sand/stone 1Sak	40.000	35.000	30.000
Pasir Bill 30Liter	85.000	83.000	84.000
Fragrant Sand 20kg/25liter	120.000	121.000	123.000
Cat Shampoo	6.000-10.000	15.000-30.000	8.000-35.000
Cat Medicines	8.000- 75.000	15.000- 40.000	8.000-35.000
Cat Toys	10.000	15.000	8.000-15.000
All Size Sandbox	15.000	18.000	15.000-20.000
Cat Plate	6.000- 10.000	15.000	8.000-15.000
Cat Scrap	5.000- 15.000	15.000	10.000
Cat's Milk	5.000	5.000	5.000
Average	29.441	31.588	31.088

Table 1: Price Comparison of Green Pets Shop with 99 Pets Shop and Naching Pets Shop

Based on table 1 is an example of a business competitor sold by *Green Pets Shop*, when compared to *99 Pets shop*, *Naching Pets Shop* the value of goods in *Green Pets Shop* is more varied, but some goods are cheaper and some of the goods are also higher because of the difference between Rp. 2,000-Rp. 40,000 compared to *99 Pets Shop*, *Naching Pets Shop*. The following is the customer data of *Green Pets Shop* from January to December in 2020.

A purchasing decision is a process of making a purchase decision that includes purchasing decision is a process of making a purchase decision that includes specific and evaluate the product or brand how good each alternative is it can solve Problem, which then a series of processes lead to the purchase decision [7].

Moon	Consumer Visits			Sales Turnover		
	Target (Person)	Realization (Person)	%	Target (IDR)	Realization (IDR)	%
January	600	550	91.67	100.000.000	75.000.000	75.00
February	600	520	86.67	100.000.000	63.520.000	63.52
March	600	300	50.00	100.000.000	35.000.000	35.00
April	600	310	51.67	100.000.000	38.129.000	38.12
May	600	295	49.17	100.000.000	42.500.000	42.50
June	600	350	58.33	100.000.000	53.000.000	53.10
July	600	450	75.00	100.000.000	49.000.000	49.00
August	600	370	61.67	100.000.000	57.650.000	57.65
September	600	310	51.67	100.000.000	60.000.000	60.00
October	600	295	49.17	100.000.000	62.590.000	62.90
November	600	320	53.33	100.000.000	68.170.000	68.17
December	600	400	66.67	100.000.000	78.100.000	78.10

Table 2: Green Pets Shop Consumer Visit Data for the January-December Period of 2020

Source: Green Pets Shop data for 2020)

Based on the information data above, it is known that the number of visits by consumers or customers who shop at the *Green Pets Shop* as well as the number of monthly turnovers of the *Green Pets Shop* for one year, namely January-December 2020, none of them reached the target. Choosing the right location will have a significant impact on sales. The location of the *Green Pets Shop* is not supported by a good parking space, because the area joins the shophouses next to the *Green Pets Shop* because those who shop in this place mostly park their vehicles on the shoulder of the road. Where the *green pets shop* business location is a road that is not too wide with quite heavy traffic. The dense traffic is one of the advantages possessed by the *Green Pets Shop*, because people passing in front of the *Green Pets Shop* have the opportunity to look / turn their heads towards the store, so the existence of the *Green Pets Shop* is increasingly known by the public. This is what encourages owners to take advantage of the crowds in front of the store by making banners with a large enough size whose content advertises products that may have cheaper prices than prices elsewhere. Examples of products that do have cheaper prices because they are to attract public interest (low prices from manufacturers / distributors).

In determining the purchase decision of other *Pets Shop*, product quality factors, cleanliness also have a very big influence in deciding on purchases because consumers also want whatever is sold or the place must be really clean and comfortable. All factors that influence purchasing decisions such as price and location are not necessarily able to create purchasing decisions for consumers and optimally, therefore it is necessary to re-evaluate how much influence they have on purchasing decisions. Based on the background that has

been stated above, the findings of the problem above are the reasons for researchers to conduct a study with the title "*The Effect of Price and Location on Purchasing Decisions at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin*".

II. HYPOTHESIS

Based on the research background and problems expressed in the introduction, the hypothesis of this research is as follows:

- H_0 Does not affect the price of goods on purchasing decisions at *Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin*
- H_1 price affects the purchase decision at *Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin*
- H_0 Location does not affect the purchase decision at *Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin*
- H_2 Location affects purchasing decisions at *Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin*
- H_0 Price and location do not affect the purchase decision at *Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin*
- H_3 Price and location affect purchasing decisions at *Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin*

III. METHODS

This study used two variables is independent variables and dependent variables. The independent variables are 1) Price symbolized X1 with indicators a) Customary Pricing, b) Price above, equal, and below market price (Above, at, or Below Market Pricing), c) Loss Price (Loss Leader Pricing), and d) Offer Price (Sealed Bid Pricing); 2) Location symbolized by the letter X2 with indicators a) Access, b) Parking Lot, and c) Expansion. While dependent variables

are symbolized by the letter Y with indicators a) Rational Perspective / functional aspect, b) Experiential Perspective/attribute aspect / symbolic, c) Behavioral Perspective / learning aspect. The source of this research data is in the form of observations, interviews, and the distribution of questionnaires to consumers and owners of Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin. This research data collection technique uses field studies which include observation activities, interviews, documenter studies, and questionnaires. The form of the questionnaire is closed meaning that the respondent is given an alternative of each answer to each question. All variables will be measured using a Likert scale. Each alternative answer is weighted as follows:

The number of populations in this study, which was calculated from January to December 2020 with an average number of 84 consumers per week due to time constraints, the researchers chose a population per week. Determination of the sample using the Slovin formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Description:

N :Sample size

N :Population size

E :Percent of looseness of inaccuracies due to sampling errors that are still estimated or desired 5%

No	Answer Choice	Score	Code
1	Strongly Agree	5	SS
2	Agree	4	S
3	Simply Agree	3	CS
4	Disagree	2	TS
5	Strongly Disagree	1	STS

Table 3: Choice/Score Code Alternative Answers

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics of Correspondents

Green Pets Shop providing products needed for animal needs, especially for cats and also providing services for veterinary consultations with direct veterinarians. The services offered are quite good to consumers because the owner of the Green Pets Shop. Mrs. Dr. RiniFajarwati, also doubles as the manager, so any criticism or suggestions from consumers are directly responded to by the Green Pets Shop, so it can develop in accordance with consumer demand.

- Green Pets Shopowners are people who participate and even go directly down in managing stores and serving consumers, creating a routine reporting system such as making daily, weekly, and monthly reports so that Green Pets Shopowners can monitor employee performance.

- An employee is a person who works at the Green Pets Shop and is paid with money or it can be said that the person who serves as a worker in a trading business to carry out the operation of his workplace in return for services in the form of money. Employees at the Green Pets Shop do not have special duties but help each other help other employees.

No	Indicator	Criterion	Sum	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Man	16	42,1
		Woman	22	57,9
2	Age Range	15-25 years old	15	39,5
		26-35 years old	11	28,9
		40-50 yearsold	8	21,1
		58 years old	4	10,5
		SMP Equivalent	8	21,1
3.	Recent Education	SMA Equivalent	20	52,6
		Diploma	3	7,9
		Bachelor	7	18,4
		Housewives	9	23,7
4.	Work	PNS(Civil Servants)	11	28,9
		Private Employees	13	34,2
		Merchant	5	13,2

Table 4: Research Correspondent Indicators

Source: Data Processed (2021)

B. Test the Validity and Reliability of Research Instruments

NO	Item	r count	r table	Cronbach's alpha	Status	
Results of the Customary Price Validity and Reliability Test (X_{1.1})						
1	Item1	0.615	0,3202	0,713	Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.293	0,3202	0,713	In Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.513	0,3202	0,713	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.591	0,3202	0,713	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 5	0.352	0,3202	0,713	Valid	Reliable
Results of the Customary Price Validity and Reliability Test (X_{1.1})						
1	Item 1	0.615	0,3202	0,713	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.513	0,3202	0,713	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.591	0,3202	0,713	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 5	0.352	0,3202	0,713	Valid	Reliable
Validity and Reliability Test Results Prices above, equal, and below the market (X_{1.2})						
1	Item1	0.425	0,3202	0,750	Valid	Reliable
2	Item2	0.550	0,3202	0,750	Valid	Reliable
3	Item3	0.688	0,3202	0,750	Valid	Reliable
4	Item4	0.250	0,3202	0,750	In Valid	Reliable
5	Item5	0.743	0,3202	0,750	Valid	Reliable
Validity and Reliability Test Results Prices above, equal, and below market (X_{1.2})						
1	Item1	0.425	0,3202	0,750	Valid	Reliable
2	Item2	0.550	0,3202	0,750	Valid	Reliable
3	Item3	0.688	0,3202	0,750	Valid	Reliable
5	Item5	0.743	0,3202	0,750	Valid	Reliable
Test Results of Validity and Reliability of Loss Price (X_{1.3})						
1	Item1	0.551	0,3202	0,685	Valid	Reliable
2	Item2	0.478	0,3202	0,685	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.426	0,3202	0,685	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.603	0,3202	0,685	Valid	Reliable
5	Item5	0.188	0,3202	0,685	In Valid	Reliable
Test Results of Validity and Reliability of Loss Price (X_{1.3})						
1	Item1	0.551	0,3202	0,685	Valid	Reliable
2	Item2	0.478	0,3202	0,685	Valid	Reliable
3	Item3	0.426	0,3202	0,685	Valid	Reliable
4	Item4	0.603	0,3202	0,685	Valid	Reliable
Test Results of Validity and Reliability of Bid Prices (X_{1.4})						
1	Item1	0.091	0,3202	0,676	In Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.392	0,3202	0,676	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.651	0,3202	0,676	Valid	Reliable

4	Itemr 4	0.405	0,3202	0,676	Valid	Reliable
5	Item5	0.657	0,3202	0,676	Valid	Reliable
Test Results of Validity and Reliability of Bid Prices (X_{1.4})						
2	Item 2	0.392	0,3202	0,676	Valid	Reliable
3	Item3	0.651	0,3202	0,676	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.405	0,3202	0,676	Valid	Reliable
5	Item5	0.657	0,3202	0,676	Valid	Reliable
Access Validity and Reliability Test Results (X_{2.1})						
1	Item1	0.371	0,3202	0,708	Valid	Reliable
2	Item2	0.666	0,3202	0,708	Valid	Reliable
3	Item3	0.584	0,3202	0,708	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.390	0,3202	0,708	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 5	0.341	0,3202	0,708	Valid	Reliable
Parking Lot Validity and Reliability Test Results (X_{2.2})						
	Item 1	0.645	0,3202	0,601	Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.498	0,3202	0,601	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.686	0,3202	0,601	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.496	0,3202	0,601	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 5	-0.142	0,3202	0,601	In Valid	Reliable
Parking Lot Validity and Reliability Test Results (X_{2.2})						
1	Item 1	0.645	0,3202	0,601	Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.498	0,3202	0,601	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.686	0,3202	0,601	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.496	0,3202	0,601	Valid	Reliable
Expansion Validity and Reliability Test Results (X_{2.3})						
1	Item 1	0.491	0,3202	0,692	Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.437	0,3202	0,692	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.400	0,3202	0,692	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.532	0,3202	0,692	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 5	0.386	0,3202	0,692	Valid	Reliable
Validity and Reliability Test Results of Rational Perspectives (Y_{1.1})						
1	Item 1	0.332	0,3202	0,757	Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.412	0,3202	0,757	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.733	0,3202	0,757	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.547	0,3202	0,757	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 5	0.665	0,3202	0,757	Valid	Reliable
Validity and Reliability Test Results of Experiential Perspectives (Y_{1.2})						
1	Item 1	0.632	0,3202	0,746	Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.505	0,3202	0,746	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.596	0,3202	0,746	Valid	Reliable

4	Item 4	0.199	0,3202	0,746	In Valid	Reliable
5	Item 5	0.655	0,3202	0,746	Valid	Reliable
Validity and Reliability Test Results of Experiential Perspectives (Y _{1.2})						
1	Item 1	0.632	0,3202	0,746	Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.505	0,3202	0,746	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.596	0,3202	0,746	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 4	0.655	0,3202	0,746	Valid	Reliable
Validity and Reliability Test Results of a Behavioral Perspective (Y _{1.3})						
1	Item 1	0.633	0,3202	0,773	Valid	Reliable
2	Item 2	0.240	0,3202	0,773	In Valid	Reliable
3	Item 3	0.700	0,3202	0,773	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 4	0.583	0,3202	0,773	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 5	0.580	0,3202	0,773	Valid	Reliable
Validity and Reliability Test Results of a Behavioral Perspective (Y _{1.3})						
1	Item 1	0.633	0,3202	0,773	Valid	Reliable
3	Item 2	0.700	0,3202	0,773	Valid	Reliable
4	Item 3	0.583	0,3202	0,773	Valid	Reliable
5	Item 4	0.580	0,3202	0,773	Valid	Reliable

Table 5: Validity and Reliability Test Results

The results of the regression equation are based on calculations using the SPSS For Windows program, namely:

$$Y = 8.901 + 0.715 X_1 + 0.050 X_2$$

The results of the regression equation are based on calculations using the SPSS For Windows program, namely:

- The Constanta value of 8,901 indicates that if there is no price and location variable, the purchase decision variable at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin is 8,901.
- The value of the regression coefficient of 0.715 means that, if there is a change that increases by 1 (one) in the price variable by assuming other factors are fixed, it will result in a change in the increase of 0.715 to the purchase decision variable at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin
- The value of the regression coefficient of 0.050 means that, if there is a change that increases by 1 (one) in the location variable by assuming other factors remain, it will result in a change in the increase of 0.050 to the purchase decision variable at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin.

Calculated t-value the variable price (X₁) 5,074 is greater than the table t value of 2,028, thus the price has a significant effect on the purchasing decision at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin. Calculated t-value in the location variable (X₂) is 0.351 less than the table t value of 2,028 thus the location does not have a significant effect on the purchasing decision at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin. The most dominant variable that affects the purchasing decision at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin is the price variable, this is known from the calculated t value is greater than the t count location variable.

The F-count value is 19,594 greater than F_{table} which is 3.27. Thus, the hypothesis proposed in the study was accepted. This means that there is a significant influence between the amount of price and location on the purchasing decision at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin.

The variable that affects the purchase decision at green *pets shop* Banjarmasin is the price variable, this is known from thecalculated tvalue is greater than thet-count location variable.

C. Test of Classical Assumptions

a) Normality Test

Fig. 2: Normality Test P-Plot Chart

This histogram chart illustrates the frequency distribution of price data, location and purchasing decisions. By looking at the chart above, it is known the frequency distribution around the normal curve line. Based on the histogram output above, it can be seen that the distribution of existing data is evenly distributed throughout the normal curve area which means that in this study it has passed one of the classical assumption tests, namely the normality test.

b) Multicollinearity Test

Collinearity Statistics	
Tolerance	VIF
0.709	1.410
0.709	1.410

Table 6: Multicollinearity Test Results

Source: Data processed 2021

The VIF values for each of them X1: 1.410, X2: 1.410, indicate that nothing exceeds from 10, while the tolerance values for each variable are X1: 0.709, X2: 0.709, indicating the approach of the number 1, thus in the regression model used there is no presence of multicollinearity.

c) Heteroskedasticity Test

This histogram chart illustrates the frequency distribution of price data, location and purchasing decisions. By looking at the chart above, it is known the frequency distribution around the normal curve line. Based on the histogram output above, it can be seen that the distribution of existing data is evenly distributed throughout the normal curve area which means that in this study it has passed one of the classical assumption tests, namely the normality test.

V. MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION ESTIMATION RESULTS

No	Variable	Regression Coefficient	tCalculate
1	Harga (x ₁)	0.715	5.074 (Sig 0.000)
2	Lokasi (x ₂)	0.050	0.351 (Sig 0.728)
Constanta		8.901	
Adjusted R Square		0.501	
F _{Count}		19.594 (sig 0.000)	
F _{Table5%}		3.27	
t _{Table5%}		2.028	

Table 7: Multiple Regression Estimation Results

Source: Data processed (2021)

Based on the table above, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$Y = 8.901 + 0.715 X_1 + 0.050 X_2$$

A. Hypothesis Testing

a) t test

The comparison of t count with t table needs to be known in advance how to determine t table, namely by the formula :

$$df = n - k$$

Information:

n = Number of Respondents

k = Number of Independent variables (x)

In table 6 above it is known that the calculated t-value for the price variable (X1) is 5,074 greater than the t-value of table 2,028 or (sig 0.000 < 0.05), thus the hypothesis proposed in the study. H1: The price affects the purchasing decision at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin, accepted.

The t-count of the location variable (X2) is 0.351 less than the t-table value of 2.028 or (sig 0.728 > 0.05) thus the hypothesis proposed in the study. H2: Location affects the purchase decision at Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin, rejected.

b) Test F

The comparison of F-count with F table needs to be known in advance how to determine f table, namely with the formula :

$$df = n - k - 1$$

Information:

n = Number of Respondents

k = Number of independent variables (x)

In table 6 above, it is known that the calculated f value is 19,594 greater than the table f which is 3.27, thus the hypothesis proposed in the study is:

H3: Price and Location influence purchasing decisions at Green Pets ShopBanjarmasin, accepted.

[7.] Tjiptono. 2014. *Pemasaran Jasa Prinsip, Penerapan dan Penelitian*. Andi: Yogyakarta.

B. Coefficient of Determination (Adjusted R Square)

The coefficient of determination is basically used to find out how much the percentage of contribution of the influence of price and location variables simultaneously or together on the variables of purchasing decisions at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin. Based on the calculation results, it is known that the adjusted value of R Square 0.501 means that the ability of the price and location variables can explain the variable purchase decisions at the Green Pets Shop Banjarmasin by 50.1%, while the remaining 49.9% is explained by other variables that were not studied in this study.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded as follows:

- The result of the multiple linear regression equation is $Y = 8.901 + 0.715 X_1 + 0.050 X_2$
- The price variable (X_1) affects the purchasing decision at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin. Judging from the calculation results, t value of 5.074 is greater than the table value of 2.028 (Sig 0.000 < 0.05).
- The location variable (X_2) does not affect the purchasing decision at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin. Judging from the calculation results t-count 0.351 is smaller than t-table 2.028 (Sig 0.728 > 0.05).
- The price and location variables simultaneously the calculated F value is 19.594 greater than the table F which is 3.27. Thus, it means that there is a significant influence between price and location on the purchasing decision at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin.
- The coefficient of determination adjusted R square of 0.501 means that the ability of the price and location variables can explain the purchase decision at the Green *Pets Shop* Banjarmasin by 50.1% while the remaining 49.9% is explained by other variables that were not studied in this study.

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